

**URGENT ISSUES IN ORGANIZING PRE-CONSCRIPTION BASIC
TRAINING AND MILITARY-PATRIOTIC EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS**

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Annotation: This article discusses the implementation of innovative educational technologies in conducting pre-prescription basic training and military-patriotic education activities in educational institutions. Today, one of the primary tasks for professors and educators is to highlight effective ways to instill military patriotism in young people and integrate innovative educational technologies into the pre-prescription basic training curriculum.

Keywords: New Uzbekistan strategy, pre-prescription basic training, educational institutions, military education, training, pedagogical technologies,

innovative approach, military-patriotic education.

To achieve progress, it is essential and necessary to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This allows us to take the shortest path to development. As stated by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, in his book "The Strategy of New Uzbekistan," we must not forget the critical importance of nurturing intellectual and cultural potential and fostering unique talents.

In organizing pre-conscription basic training and military-patriotic education in educational institutions, the pedagogical skills and creative approach of the training leader play a crucial role. Today, one of the tools that help enhance the teacher's skills is modern pedagogical technologies. Modern pedagogical technology is the product of the development of contemporary didactics and pedagogy. If each modern educator applies existing pedagogical technologies in their lessons, they will undoubtedly achieve positive results. The goal of today's teachers is to cultivate well-rounded young individuals, provide them with comprehensive education and training, equip them with necessary information, teach them to think independently, develop their knowledge and life skills, and instill in them feelings of patriotism and love for their people. These noble goals can be achieved through lessons conducted based on advanced pedagogical and innovative technologies.

The organization of pre-conscription basic training and military-patriotic education, like other fields, consists of the educational process (the activity of the training leader) and the learning process (the activity of the cadet or student). The cadets' activities in the learning process involve acquiring knowledge, skills, and

competencies, while the educational process is closely linked to the training process.

In the application of pedagogical and innovative technologies in military education, it is important to consider the unique aspects of the training. Hence, developing and fundamentally reforming the existing educational system, as well as improving training programs from the perspective of technologization, remains an important and urgent issue for field specialists.

Military training is conducted in theoretical, practical, demonstrative, tactical, tactical formation, and control forms, with most of it being practical, based on the requirements of the general military regulations of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Training in shooting preparedness involves instructions and guidelines for handling training and combat weapons, with most training closely connected to the educational and material base. This highlights the specific aspects of military education and training.

It is worth noting that each training leader must be able to select effective technologies, utilize efficient and economical forms of education to enhance learners' activity, and emphasize the importance of the training leader's pedagogical skills and creative approach in the preparation process. In this regard, it is advisable for the training leader to critically evaluate their activities without deviating from the principles of military training, relying on the experience gained in applying advanced new teaching methods.

Going forward, training leaders must logically and correctly implement advanced pedagogical innovative technologies at a high level, analyze facts during the technologization process, generalize, draw conclusions, and adhere strictly to professional qualifications.

Currently, there are different approaches to technologizing education. One approach defines teaching technologies as equipping with all teaching tools, requiring the technicization of the educational process. Another approach views technology as a method of providing educational practice with new or modernized knowledge. Here, technology is considered the application of scientific principles and practices of education.

The issue of implementing new pedagogical innovative technologies in the process of teaching pre-conscription basic training in educational institutions can be viewed from two perspectives without conflicting with the principles of conducting military training.

In the first approach, the effectiveness of subject classes is linked not only to the application of new pedagogical innovative technologies but also to the requirements of the general military regulations of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as directly to the educational and material base, material support, and the preparation level of the training leader. This approach does not foresee the application of new innovative technologies to practical training.

The second approach interprets the teaching process as consistently and systematically organized while fully considering the content of the first approach.

Analyses indicate that in both approaches, the specificity of conducting training in military education retains its significance. The process of teaching military education is carried out in a logical sequence.

This sequence includes: setting tasks for cadets; generating interest in knowledge among cadets; cadets' acceptance of new material; analyzing and generalizing the accepted material; forming scientific concepts; mastering laws;

consolidating and improving acquired knowledge; forming skills and competencies; applying knowledge, skills, and competencies; checking cadets' acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies; analyzing the results of education.

This sequence does not negate the interpretation of the teaching process as consistently and systematically organized. The implementation of innovative technologies in military education strengthens the mutual connection between the educator (teaching) and the learner (learning) and activates their activities in knowledge delivery and acquisition, creating a creative environment.

The lessons conducted under the "Modern Lesson" concept in educational institutions result from advanced teachers applying new innovative technologies in their specialized subjects. However, the modern lessons observed are related to conducting visual and open lessons according to the educational method plan of the educational institutions for certain topics within the sections or chapters of subjects.

Through innovative teaching, it is advisable to aim for the following outcomes: developing the standards and criteria for an innovative approach in the application of pedagogical technologies; preparing scientific methodological recommendations on innovative approaches in applying pedagogical technologies in military training; conducting initial research on innovative approaches as a methodological issue scientifically, theoretically, and practically in military training; introducing innovative approaches as a new teaching technology in organizing and conducting military training; methodologically classifying the concept of innovative approach; developing the content, forms, and methods of applying innovative approaches in conducting military training.

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